

Impact of social media marketing on the tourism demand of Imus City

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Abstract

Technology has become a fast-moving force across the world and is affecting the mobility of people and industries. Social media is known to be used as a form of marketing by the tourism industry nowadays since it has been proven to have less cost than other types of marketing. However, there are also some issues of using social media platforms in marketing tourist destinations to increase tourism demand in certain places. This study investigated the effects and possible changes that social media can give a remarkable impact to both tourists and the tourism industry in Imus City. Quantitative research method was used in the form of online survey questionnaires in a 5-point Likert scales were distributed to 100 participants aging from 18-59 years old using quota sampling. Responses were analyzed using frequency/percentage, mean, standard deviation, and Likert scale ranking on the respondents' demographic profile. The ranking of effectiveness was also used to analyze social media platforms. Results revealed that the best social media platform to use in marketing tourist destinations was Facebook. A positive perception of the tourists using social media for browsing tourist destinations was also shown in the analysis. The study's findings suggested that social media platforms were used by the people to conveniently look for a place to visit and were proven to be an effective form of marketing tool for tourism. However, tourists' decisions can be influenced positively or negatively based on online reviews and ratings.

Keywords: Social media; Marketing; Demand; Tourism; Imus City.

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Introduction

Today's globalization has pursued new marketing strategies for many businesses and organizations. These new marketing strategies include the improvement of internet communication by using different social media platforms. By this means, these channels have become an approach that are used for marketing at a lesser cost but can involve more market (Kiráľová & Pavlíček, 2015).

Social media has always been a fast-moving field as of now. Information and communication have changed rapidly. Slightly more than a year ago, several social media factors introduced the content format stories. The business is pouring their money through social advertisements. For example, YouTube vloggers upload a video with an advertisement on it; when viewers watch it and finish the advertisement, the vloggers might have an extra income (Lua, 2018). It goes without saying that social media have become the trend of time.

Trending is a rapid increase in public interest and attention. Nowadays, social media impacts our lives greatly. Based on what we saw through social media, public posts might get viral because of the people's same interest that catches their attention. Social trends are not always created by the majority but mostly, most of society follows this. It is an ever-changing aspect of today's generation (Bennett, 2017).

One of the most sought-after economic fields in society today is tourism. As defined, tourism is a process of people moving outside their common surroundings to other geographical areas for personal or business intentions. This may be related to economic, social, or cultural aspects. It plays a great role in the development of a country, region, or even cities. One of the world's fastest-growing industries is the tourism industry (World Tourism Organization, 2021).

The promotion of tourism products has been highly competitive as time passes by. The rise of technological advancements has made tourism organizations adjust to using the internet as a means of marketing for tourism. Sahin and Sengün (2015) mentioned that the utilization of technology has been used in tourism marketing to attract its market and go along with the trend of technology. Not just by using the internet but also by other platforms are used to approach the tourism market and improve the tourism organization's way of communication.

Social media is widely known to be an internet application that spreads information based on the contents and experiences of its users on the internet (Tussyadiah et al., 2011). Forums, video dissemination, photo archives, and other social networking sites are some of the various social media platforms that exist. There are different usage patterns and kinds of communication in using social media such as one-to-many or many-to-many (Fotis et al., 2013). All in all, the electronic word-of-mouth (E-WoM) that is being disseminated on the web provides opportunities for a more tailored information experience for its users.

The Electronic Word of Mouth (e-Wom) describes a part of social media's essential roles in the marketing of tourism since it influences the analyzing decision of the tourists on choosing where to visit (Živković et al., 2014). The birth of cyberspace paves way for social media to take place in the marketing of tourism products and reach the target market of tourism organizations. Social media will be a great opportunity for tourism organizations to target customers and engage with them based on their social media activity to capture their interests.

The researchers decided to conduct the study in Imus, Cavite which is the Flag Capital of the Philippines. Imus City was originally connected to a place called El Viejo which is now presently known as "Kawit." In 1762, a parish church was established in the barangay now known as Bayan Luma. The church was destroyed by a typhoon in September of 1776 (Diocese of Imus, n.d.). The total population of Imus during the year 2020 census was 540,548 (City Population, 2020). There are some tourist spots in Imus, Cavite, and one of them is the Imus Cathedral. Imus Cathedral is one of the noticeable churches which stand tall at Imus. The present church was established by Fr. Nicolas Becerra when he was serving from 1821 to 1840, and it was built of bricks and stones (Layug, 2017).

Buted et al. (2014) pointed out that one of the means to faster disseminate information on target markets of tourism establishments that offers less cost is using social media platforms. However, there are also some disadvantages in using social media for marketing tourism such as unfair criticisms because of the misinformation of customers' opinions, thoughts, and expressions they live in social media.

The study aims to investigate the outlooks of respondents and the impacts of marketing using social media in the city of Imus. The following research objectives are aimed at being achieved at the end of this study:

- 1.) To explore the outlooks of the respondents about using social media in choosing a tourist attraction.
- 2.) To analyze the positive and negative effects / impacts of social media marketing in Imus City's tourism demand.
- 3.) To determine the best social media platforms to be used in tourism marketing.

Statement of the Problem

There has been an influx of technological advancements in the world. The Philippines is one of the countries to experience these phenomena. Today, the rise of the internet has affected a lot including the way of thinking of people, the way we live, and even how we communicate especially in these times of crisis. In line with this, there is an increase in popularity in the use of social media platforms today which are used by many tourism organizations as their marketing tools would increase tourism demand. The questions that the research specifically aims to answer are the following:

1. What is the profile of tourists?
 - 1.1 age
 - 1.2 gender
 - 1.3 civil status
 - 1.4 place of origin
2. What are the respondents' outlook about using social media in choosing a tourist attraction?
3. What are the impacts of marketing through social media on the tourism demand in Imus City?
4. What are the effective social media platforms used for marketing tourism?

Related Studies

Many of us have been tourists, but defining tourism can be difficult. Walton (2020) defined the term 'Tourism' as the process of going away from the origin place for personal intentions such as pleasure, recreation, and relaxation by experiencing the services of the places they visit. Tourism development has also been considered by many countries. Unfortunately, those countries usually overestimated their cost.

Social media helps the tourists to connect to reviews and suggestions of many people, and this includes friends in their social media accounts and other tourists that they have not even met. Tourism businesses grabbed the opportunity to use social media to promote tourist spots and tourism products (Mukherjee & Nagabhushanam, 2017).

Social media plays an essential part in the dissemination of opinions and information among consumers and good advertising using E-WoM in the tourism industry since the industry is very reliant on the good image of a destination. The tourism field practices sorting out the benefits of the different social media channels; because through promotion, people will know the place and frequently visit it (Zeng & Gerritsen, 2014).

Communication is a vital part of marketing products and services. Marketing refers to the creation of relationships between the customers and clients of a business (Atienza, 2019). Social media is one of the means to best market tourism products since it can be used to communicate with potential customers and promote the products of tourism businesses with them. This is why marketing managers should carefully study the changes in trends, especially communication and advertising forms with the customers.

The connection and interaction between businesses in tourism sectors and their clients are one of the important functions of social media which relate to the demand and supply in the industry (Királ'ová & Pavlíčeka, 2015). It explains that varieties of social media help in the tourism industry by playing a role in the supply and demand since these platforms are used to communicate with tourists, monitor, and evaluate their behaviors and views with the tourism businesses.

In the most recent decade, there has been a large rise in the usage of social media. Social media changed many businesses and organizations to communicate with their target market. For the tourism sector, the use of the internet gave a boost to travel marketing. From how the travelers search and look for potential tourist destinations, to the activities that they can do when they arrive. These new ways of using social media have affected the tourists' decision-making and tourism marketing (Hostinsky, 2019).

Khan and Jan (2015) stipulated that social media marketing is another technique that pretty much companies embrace to virtually reach their target market. Web-based platforms are the main way out to extend a big volume of people in a not very costly way. It is said that companies in the entertainment industry were the first ones to use marketing through social media and promoting their services and products.

Gohil (2015) also pointed out in his study that social media is an extreme form of marketing tool which can help businesses in increasing income and reaching their target market. Since the tourism industry is fast-growing, businesses in this industry can use social media to level up their form of marketing so that they can practice brand awareness among customers, positive word-of-mouth advertising, increase customer loyalty, and retention, and create a reputable view for a tourist destination.

The tourism sector is widely affected by the emerging social media platform use of people especially those in the younger generation (Sahin & Sengün, 2015). The products in the tourism and hospitality industry are being critiqued and reviewed carefully by many people. The products and services of industry should maintain a good image, this is why tourism-related businesses should manage their social media accounts properly and hire personnel to monitor and control these accounts. Since the younger generation is the most likely to give reviews, tourism businesses should be careful not to receive any negative comments and reviews to prevent their brand image from appearing negatively to other customers.

Social media has a vital part in promoting tourism. It helps the tourism industry to get the perspective of the tourists or customers and market tourism products. Social media unites a variety of travel groups and shares their insights and other related travel experiences that bind many travel lovers. With that, the knowledge of people about the place has broadened and gone beyond their locals. Today, most travelers decide about their trip based on the reviews, ratings, and experiences published on social media (Vaisakh et al., 2020).

Social media has brought a lot of changes when it comes to advertising and marketing a product to consumers. Tourism sites on the internet are popular on social media networking sites. Most of the people in our generation are into online social networks. Milano et al. (2011) expressed their assessment on the behavior, effects, and usage of the touristic version of Web 2.0 or Travel 2.0. It influences the business and image of companies, organizations, and destinations stressing the importance of the variety of tools in the hands of a tourist. To improve the status of tourism websites it is important to consider adopting such tools. The two online social networks that have been considered are Facebook and Twitter.

The study of Buted et al. (2014) mentioned five (5) particular social media platforms which are often used by customers and businesses in the tourism and hospitality industry. These platforms are YouTube, Facebook, blogs, Twitter, and various sites. The best way to disseminate information is by social media channels and reaching the target market of the tourism businesses which makes it an effective tool for marketing. However, as time passes by, there are also new social media platforms that are becoming much more popular with customers and businesses than before. This shows the fast-changing application and usage of social media and technology which have been affecting the tourism and hospitality industry and its marketing strategies.

An analysis of the attitudes of customers in the tourism industry is an important factor for businesses and one of the essential tools to use is social media. By using these platforms, the behaviors of tourists are being affected, and it is shown because there is an addition with the sales and reviews from past consumers. The uniqueness of propositional value in every offer as well as tailored customer experience in tourism is important to build a successful service-based brand.

Mangan (2015) argued that social media greatly impacts the tourism industry. It has made a huge impact on the tourism industry. Customers can research their trips and be informed to make decisions about their travels. Consumers are also able to share their personal experiences by using social networking sites of the restaurant, hotel, or airline that they visited. There is a vast amount of information that is available to travelers on the internet. The information provided by the platform allows people to give insights into their experiences on the destination by photos, clips, and words. Because of this innovation, the marketers of the destination are affected as well as the tourists who use the platforms. There is overlying positive and negative feedback and reviews that may happen which can impact the brand image of the destination, and it is almost uncontrollable.

Social media is known to have a benefit in using it for marketing and communicating with consumers since it is known to be cost-efficient and unbiased. The image of a destination is being influenced by the reviews of people in social media, and it can be easily done since cyberspace can reach a broad audience and can be simply accessed around the world.

Wang et al. (2012) pointed out that social presence is reached by tourists when they exchange textual files, pictures, and videos on social media platforms. This also increases the possibility for travelers to take part in various activities when they can express their journey on the web. The effect and utilization of social media marketing strategies are important to satisfy tourism demand worldwide because of the introduction, creation, and ease of access of the internet, travelers have changed how they plan and book their trips to a specific destination. Businesses familiarize themselves with the use of the internet to gather data and information from searching about tours on the web or social media. Accessing data and information is so easy and it changes how the data is generated and distributed. Marketers may use social media to vitalize and motivate the interaction of tourists to help the growing attention of tourists to a certain place (Jashi, 2013).

According to De las Heras-Pedrosa et al. (2020), a sector where the introduction of innovative and modern technologies of communication impacts greatly is the tourism industry. This includes mainly the ability to create an effective virtual existence and proper social media management to attract travelers and make the cities more visible to people. Using social media to market a place or tourist destination is one of the greatest ideas to use in today's generation. Eight (8) out of every ten (10) consumers think that social media is a good platform in product and brand interaction.

Social media has proven to be an effective tool for marketing (Atienza, 2019). Tourism-related businesses have been using these platforms to reach their customers and to increase income. Studies show that social media helps in building a brand image in a tourist destination and increases customer loyalty (Gohil, 2015). However, there may be some disadvantages of marketing through social media that were not mentioned in other related studies. Tham et al. (2020) argued that besides having mixed influential effects, social media changed the tourism perspectives and landscapes. Tourists often engage in social media channels to make decisions such as choosing a destination. However, due to technological advancements today, there may be some changes with the platforms mostly used by businesses and their customers. There is no study that has a focus on the effects of social media platforms being used for marketing on Imus City's tourism demand. The researchers aim to analyze the positive and negative impacts of social media on the tourism demand in Imus City and determine the current social media platforms used by customers in looking for and evaluating a tourist destination.

Methodology

This study is a quantitative type of research which employed survey questionnaires to collect data for the study. It also used a descriptive method to obtain the impact of tourism demand on using social media in marketing tourism. Creswell and Creswell (2017) indicated that a way to test objective theories is by using quantitative research where the connection of variables is being analyzed. Using instruments, the measurement of the said variables is done to statistically analyze the data gathered. In connection with the

hypothesis of this research, the researchers used this design to test whether social media as a marketing tool for tourism may have an impact on the tourism demand of Imus. McCombes (2019) added that a descriptive method aims to accurately and systematically investigate one or two variables.

To best address the research objectives, this method enabled the researchers to explore the phenomena pertaining to the effects of social media on the tourism demand of Imus City. The descriptive method of this research aims to explore the phenomenon and learn its effects without changing anything to it. In gathering information, the researchers aimed to learn about the positive and negative impact of social media marketing toward the tourism demand of Imus City.

Sampling Procedures & Instrumentation

The samples of this research from which the data were collected are 100 respondents in the age range of 18-59 years old, who are residing in the Philippines only, and who have experienced visiting Imus City, represented the total population of the research, since these are capable to travel. The researchers have decided not to include the residents of Imus City to explore more about the outlooks of the tourists outside the area.

The study used quota sampling. Yang and Banamah (2014) defined quota sampling which contains the sample to a particular criteria list such as social group, age, or gender. One of the known ways to use quota sampling is by dividing the sample based on age. With that, researchers decided to survey a limit/quota number of participants that are from 18-59 years old and are residing in the Philippines only. Quota sampling assures that the sample only involves people who met the characteristics set in the study being researched. This procedure fitted in with the study, as the researchers decided and created quotas for the market research samples to be useful in collecting data. The researchers sent Google form links to 100 residents residing in the Philippines aged 18 to 59 years old, who met the criteria set by the researchers.

The research instrument was in the form of an online questionnaire. A questionnaire is a structured form consisting of a formalized series of questions designed to collect information from the respondents that can be thought of as a kind of written interview. Statistical analysis was used to present in tabular form, interpret and analyze data in a survey questionnaire. The researchers adopted a 5-Point Likert Scale to carry out the social media marketing impact on the tourism demand of Imus City. Closed-ended questions were also employed in the questionnaire to support the quantitative design of the study and to have more accurate results. The respondents' answers were collected and analyzed by the researchers through statistical analysis.

Data Collection & Analysis Procedures

The questionnaire has been pilot tested by researchers and has already undergone reliability testing which resulted in scores of 0.90 for the correlation coefficient and 0.95 for the Spearman-Brown correlation. The questionnaire was also validated by the research adviser before the data collection was conducted. The data were collected using an online survey questionnaire. All data collected were analyzed using various statistical tools such as percentage, ranking, mean, and standard deviation.

Tools for Analysis of Data

The researchers used the mean and standard deviation to determine the positive and negative impacts on the tourism demand in marketing using the social media in tourism based on the answers of the respondents as well as to explore the outlooks of the respondents about using social media in choosing a tourist attraction. Percentage and ranking of effectiveness were also used to determine the most effective

social media platforms used today which have affected the views and decisions of tourists and the impact on the tourism demand of Imus City. Therefore, the outcome of all the data collected concluded with the output of the research. The researchers used Analysis Toolpak in Microsoft Excel to analyze data.

Results and Discussion

Profile of the Respondents

Table 1. Age Frequency Distribution

Age	Frequency (N)	Percentage (%)
18-25	84	84%
26-30	9	9%
31-35	1	1%
36-40	1	1%
41-45	4	4%
46-50	1	1%
Total	100	100%

Table 1 shows the age frequency distribution of the respondents. The table shows that 84% belong to the age group of 18 to 25 years old; 9% of the respondents belong to the age group of 26 to 30; and 4% of the respondents are within the age range of 41 to 45 years old. The age groups of 31 to 35 years old, 36 to 40 years old, and 46 to 50 years old has 1% each. As stated in the study of Perrin (2015), those who have the highest potential in using social media to the extent, with a percentage of 90% are young adults from 18 to 29 years old. However, since the year 2010, 11% of those who use social media are from the ages 65 years and older which have increased at a triple rate. At present, people who are within the age of 65 years and older (35%) have used social media, compared to 2% during 2005.

Figure 1. Gender Frequency Distribution

Figure 1 shows the gender frequency distribution of the respondents. The chart illustrates that 63% are female participants and 37% are male participants.

Table 2. Civil Status Frequency Distribution

Civil Status	Frequency (N)	Percentage (%)
Single	89	89%
Married	7	7%
Separated	1	1%
Rather not say	3	3%
Total	100	100%

Table 2 shows the civil status frequency distribution of the respondents. The table presented that 89% are single; 7% are married; 3% of the respondents would rather not reveal their civil status; and 1% of the respondents is separated.

Figure 3. Place of Origin Frequency Distribution

Figure 3 shows the place of origin frequency distribution of the respondents. The chart reveals that 36% of the respondents are from Bacoor; 16% are from Cavite; 15% are from Manila; 5% are from Dasmariñas; 4% from other geographical locations of the Philippines; respondents from Kawit, Marikina City, and Negros Occidental are 2% each; and the rest of the respondents are from Albay, Amadeo, Bataan, Bico, Davao City, Naic, Occidental Mindoro, Pampanga, Parañaque City, Quezon City, Samar, Surigao Del Sur, Tacloban City, Tanza, and Taytay, Rizal with 1% each respectively.

Figure 4. Respondents Who Visited Tourist Attraction in Imus City

Figure 4 shows that 87% of the respondents have visited tourist attractions in Imus City, while 13% of the respondents have not visited any tourist attractions in Imus City.

Figure 5. Travel Motivations of the Respondents in Visiting Tourist Attractions in Imus City

Figure 5 presents the motivation of the respondents in visiting the tourist attractions in Imus City. The results reveal that, in terms of personal interest, 41 or 22% of the respondents answered visiting family members and relatives as motivation; 35 or 18.8% of the respondents are motivated by relaxation; 33 or 17.7% visit tourist attractions in Imus City for school-related activities; 12 or 6.5% of the respondents state that they are motivated to conduct/transact business. Lastly, the remaining 3.2% of the respondents have other motivations for visiting tourist attractions in Imus City. Walton (2020) said that tourists who are travelling to various places outside their origin. He mentioned that tourists go to different destinations because of various reasons such as pleasure, relaxation, or leisure. Therefore, tourists have various travel motivations as to why they visit a particular place.

Figure 6. Percentage of Respondents who looked through Social Media Platforms to determine which place in Imus City to Visit

Figure 6 shows the percentage of respondents who looked through social media platforms to determine which place in Imus City to visit. The chart shows that 86% of the respondents have looked through social media platforms to determine which place in Imus City they would like to visit, while 14% of the respondents have not investigated any social media platforms. Hostinsky (2019) mentioned that travelers tend to use social media to look for travel destinations and places to visit. Thus, new ways of social media use are affecting the tourism sector and the decision making of tourists.

Figure 7 presents the summary of results of the statements regarding the outlook of respondents about using social media platforms in choosing a tourist attraction. Thirty-eight (38%) of the respondents answer that social media always influence them in choosing a specific place to visit. Thirty-nine (39%) of the respondents who always admire a place because of the social media influencers that give positive feedback about it.

Figure 7. Summary of Results about the respondents’ outlook on using Social Media in choosing a Tourist Attraction

Forty percent (40%) of the respondents answer both always and frequently that social media helps them look at the promotion of a place that attracts them to visit. Thirty percent (30%) who occasionally use social media to write a review about their trip. Forty-four (44%) of respondents who regularly use social media sites to have ideas about their next trip. Thirty-eight percent (38%) of respondents always use social media to review customer feedback before they visit Imus City.

Social media is known to have a benefit in using it for marketing and communicating with consumers since it is known to be cost-efficient and unbiased (Kongar & Adebayo, 2021). Because of this, past consumers may impact others with their decisions when they use social media for communication. The image of a destination is being influenced by the reviews of people in social media, and it can be easily done since cyberspace can reach a broad audience and can be simply accessed around the world.

Figure 8. Summary of Results of the Impacts of Social Media Platforms to Tourism Demand of Imus City

Figure 8 illustrates the summary of results for the statements about the positive and negative impacts of social media platforms on the tourism demand of Imus City. Forty-eight percent (48%) of the respondents answered strongly agree that a positive online review of a place make them want to visit a tourist destination. Forty-four percent (44%) of the respondents agree that ratings on social media help them decide if they would go to their chosen destination.

Fifty-three percent (53%) of the respondents strongly agree that social networking sites help them to research and be informed of their trip, while 35% of the respondents strongly agree that accommodation reservations through social media are faster than calling the establishment. Forty-three (43%) of the respondents strongly agree that they find it convenient to look for tourist attractions in Imus City through social media. Thirty-four percent (34%) of the respondents who strongly agree find it convenient to book accommodations and restaurants in Imus City through social media, while 55% of the respondents strongly agree that social media helps the tourism industry to improve service.

As stated in the study of Sahin and Sengün (2015), positive and negative impacts on social media platform use and its different factors, has varying impacts, again, positively and negatively. Social media marketing is one of the best ways to reach tourists. The tourism sector is widely affected by the widespread social media use by the people, especially the younger generations. Since the younger generation is the most likely to give reviews, tourism businesses should be careful not to receive any negative comments and reviews to prevent their brand image from appearing negatively to other customers.

Table 3. Ranking of Effectiveness of the Social Media Platforms Best to Use in Finding a Tourist Destination in Imus City

Social Media Platforms	Frequency (N)	Rank	Percent	Interpretation
Facebook	73	1	85%	Highly Effective
Instagram	5	2	6%	Lowly Effective
YouTube	3	3	4%	Lowly Effective
Google	2	4	2%	Lowly Effective
Pinterest	1	6	1%	Lowly Effective
Twitter	1	6	1%	Lowly Effective
Klook/Tripadvisor	1	6	1%	Lowly Effective
Total	86		100%	

Interpretation: Above 60% = Highly Effective; Between 20%-59% = Moderately Effective; Below 20% = Lowly Effective

Table 3 indicates the ranking of effectiveness of the social media platforms best to use in finding a tourist destination in Imus City. The table shows that 85% of the respondents use Facebook in looking for tourist destinations in Imus City, rank 1, highly effective; 6% of the respondents use Instagram, rank 2; 4% of the respondents use YouTube, rank 3; 2% of the respondents for the use of Google, rank 4; while 1% of the respondents use Pinterest, Twitter, and Klook/TripAdvisor, with rank 5 and as lowly effective respectively. The researchers only included those respondents who answered that they have experienced using social media in looking for a tourist attraction.

The results of Table 3 related to the study of Buted et al. (2014) wherein they stated five particular social media platforms (YouTube, Facebook, blogs, Twitter, and various sites), that are often used by businesses and customers in the industries of tourism and hospitality. Milano et al. (2011) also mentioned some examples of social media tools that can help improve websites related to tourism which are Facebook and Twitter. The researchers included some of the social media platforms mentioned by these researchers that are in trend of being used today.

In Table 4, in terms of respondents' outlook about using social media in choosing a tourist attraction, most respondents rated 'always' in regularly using social media sites to have ideas about their next trip ($M=4.11$, $SD=0.97$); social media helps them to look at the promotion of a place to visit ($M=4.11$, $SD=0.96$); and social media influences me on choosing a specific place to visit ($M=4.05$, $SD=0.91$). They also 'frequently' admire a place because of the social media influencers that give positive feedback about it ($M=3.97$, $SD=1.02$), use social media to review customer feedback before visiting Imus City ($M=3.9$, $SD=1.15$) and to write a review about their trip ($M=3.38$, $SD=1.26$). Table 4 has a mean of 3.92 and has a standard deviation of 1.045 which establishes a decision that most of the respondents have frequently experienced the statements regarding their outlook about using social media in choosing a tourist attraction.

Table 4. Mean and Standard Deviation of Respondents' Outlook About Using Social Media in Choosing a Tourist Attraction

	Statement	Mean	Standard Deviation	Interpretation
1.	I regularly use social media sites to have ideas about my next trip.	4.11	0.97	Always
2.	Social media helps me to look at the promotion of a place that attracts me to visit.	4.11	0.96	Always
3.	Social media influences me on choosing a specific place to visit.	4.05	0.91	Always
4.	I admire a place because of the social media influencers that give positive feedback about it.	3.97	1.02	Frequently
5.	I use social media to review customer feedback before I visit Imus City.	3.90	1.15	Frequently
6.	I use social media to write a review about my trip.	3.38	1.26	Frequently
Average Weighted Mean		3.92	1.045	Frequently

Interpretation: Below 1.00 = Never; 1.00-1.99 = Rarely; 2.00-2.99 = Occasionally; 3.00-3.99 = Frequently; 4.00-5.00 = Always

It shows that respondents always have increased their level of satisfaction at the end of the visit. The result relates to the study of Zeng and Gerritsen (2014) who stated that the tourism industry relies on social media as it has many positive impacts coming through it like, destination promotions and reputation, consumer feedback, cascading of information, and advertising. With that, it has an important role in the industry, and they take advantage of social media outlets because, through the promotion, people will know the place and frequently visit it.

Table 5. Mean and Standard Deviation of Respondents' Levels of Satisfaction about the Impacts of Social Media Platforms

	Statement	Mean	Standard Deviation	Interpretation
1.	Social media helps the tourism industry to improve service.	4.36	0.88	Strongly Agree
2.	Social networking sites help me to research and be informed for my trip.	4.32	0.89	Strongly Agree
3.	Positive online review of a place makes me want to visit it.	4.26	0.87	Strongly Agree
4.	Ratings on social media helps me to decide if I would go to my chosen destination.	4.16	0.87	Strongly Agree
5.	I find it convenient to look for tourist attractions in Imus city through social media.	4.11	0.98	Strongly Agree
6.	I think that accommodation reservations through social media are faster than calling the establishment.	3.91	1.03	Agree
7.	I find it convenient to book accommodations and restaurants in Imus City through social media.	3.89	1.00	Agree
Average Weighted Mean		4.14	0.931	Frequently

Interpretation: Below 1.00 = Never; 1.00-1.99 = Rarely; 2.00-2.99 = Occasionally; 3.00-3.99 = Frequently; 4.00-5.00 = Always

In Table 5, which reveals the respondents' levels of satisfaction about the impacts of social media platforms, results show that most respondents strongly agree that social media helps the tourism industry to improve service ($M=4.36$, $SD=0.88$); social networking sites help them to research and be informed for their trip ($M=4.32$, $SD=0.89$); positive online review of a place makes me want to visit it ($M= 4.26$, $SD=0.87$); ratings on social media helps me to decide if they would go to their chosen destination ($M=4.16$, $SD=0.87$); and they find it convenient to look for tourist attractions in Imus City through social media ($M=4.11$, $SD=0.98$). They also agree that accommodation reservations through social media are faster than calling the establishment ($M=3.91$, $SD=1.03$); and they find it convenient to book accommodations and restaurants in Imus city through social media ($M=3.89$, $SD=1.00$). Table 5 has a mean of 4.14 and a standard deviation of 0.93, which means that most of the respondents strongly agree about the positive and negative impact of using social media platforms.

The result of the interpretation could be compared with the study by Vaisakh et al. (2020) which revealed that in the tourism industry, the use of social media has an important part when it comes to promoting tourism. It helps the tourism industry to get the perspective of the tourists or customers and market tourism products. Social media unites a variety of travel groups and shares their insights and other related travel experiences that bind many travel lovers. With that, the knowledge of people about the place has broadened and gone beyond their locals. Today, most travelers decide about their trip based on the reviews, ratings, and experiences published on social media.

It can be further understood that most of the respondents strongly agree that using social media platforms has an advantage and can have a positive impact. As stated in the study of Mukherjee and Nagabhushanam (2017), digital technology is a trend nowadays and social media is part of the evolution, as it binds the travelers through the opinions and based on the experiences of the masses on their social network and like-minded travelers they have never even known and seen. Tourism organizations use great developing technology by escalating their promotions of destinations and products through social media with the sole purpose of reaching out to millions of people. The disadvantages of using social media platforms the younger generation is the most likely to give reviews, tourism businesses should be careful not to receive any negative comments and reviews to prevent their brand image from appearing negatively to other customers (Sahin & Sengün, 2015). Negative feedback from customers will have an impact on potential customers as it will be a hindrance for them not to look up the product. Aside from being the most engaged in social media, they also have a great contribution to the tourism demand of a particular destination because of the promotion that they see on social media platforms.

Conclusions

Most of the respondents belonged to the age group of 18-25 years old. Majority were female but still, there were several male respondents. As to the civil status, the respondents were mostly single; most respondents are from Bacoor City; and the rest were from different places in the Philippines. Social media was the most sought-after platform used by people to look for a place to visit or before they undertake a business or pleasure trip. Social media marketing has affected tourism demand since it was used by people to find a place to visit, read reviews, and ratings which can affect their decision of choosing a place to visit. Hence, social media helped the tourism industry by helping tourists in choosing a tourist attraction to visit and to improve tourism establishments services through faster reservation and highlight reviews online from customers both domestic and international tourists. It also appeared that positive online reviews and ratings affected the decision of tourists to visit places. However, there should be proper utilization of the platforms to prevent us from using them at a disadvantage for both the tourists and the destination.

Of the many popular social media platforms, Facebook was considered the most effective social media platform for marketing tourist spots at present. Although people tend to use various social media platforms, it has become the most popular and user-friendly website, since it was much more convenient when looking for tourist attractions, book reservations, and it easily gave them knowledge about their trip.

Recommendations

The local government of Imus can employ social media to improve their service in the tourism industry through much faster and more convenient reservations. They can also develop and maintain tourist attractions on Imus and implement tourist attraction schemes, as well as encourage the locals of the city to participate in their tourism-related activities. Tourism-related establishments should maintain a good brand image since people give online reviews which may be good or not at all. Hence, the impact on the success or failure of the tourism industry in the City of Imus. Since most people use social media to look for a travel destination, the local government should utilize it, especially Facebook as it is the most used social media platform to promote and reach their target market. They should also use social media to spread information about a specific tourist spot because people use social media to research about the place they want to visit.

The locals may help in developing and protecting the tourist spots in Imus City. They may also provide services for the tourists and show the culture of Imus. Locals may also work with the Local Government of Imus in participating in its tourism-related activities by means of using social media platforms to promote the tourist attractions of Imus. A similar study may be conducted in the future as new social media platforms are being introduced to tourists/consumers. Future researchers may explore the other fields in the tourism of Imus City and explore the advantages and disadvantages of social media use as a marketing tool.

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